

A REVIEW ARTICLE ON ATOPIC DERMATITIS PATHOPHYSIOLOGY, SKIN BARRIER DYSFUNCTION AND HOW ECTOINE AND PUMPKIN SEED EXTRACT HELP TO REPAIR SKIN BARRIER AND REDUCE INFLAMMATORY RESPONSE

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ABSTRACT

Atopic dermatitis (AD) is a chronic inflammatory skin disorder characterized by impaired skin barrier function, intense pruritus, and immune dysregulation. The current review study explores the potential benefits of combining Ectoine and Pumpkin Seed Extract in topical formulations to improve AD symptoms. Ectoine, a cyclic amino acid derivative and extremolyte, exerts strong protective effects on cellular structures through preferential hydration, reducing transepidermal water loss (TEWL), enhancing membrane fluidity, and improving skin hydration. Additionally, pumpkin seed extract, rich in unsaturated fatty acids, tocopherols, carotenoids, and phenolic compounds, demonstrates potent antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and wound-healing activities, pumpkin extract also downregulates pro-inflammatory cytokines such as TNF- α and IL-6 while enhancing antioxidant enzymes, including SOD, CAT, and GPx. The integration of Ectoine's barrier-stabilizing properties with the anti-

inflammatory and regenerative effects of pumpkin extract presents a promising synergistic strategy for improving skin barrier function, reducing inflammation, and alleviating AD-associated symptoms. This combined approach may offer an effective, safe, and natural alternative for the topical management of AD.

KEYWORDS: Atopic dermatitis; Ectoine; Pumpkin seed extract; Skin barrier; Inflammation; Cytokines; Transepidermal water loss (TEWL); Filaggrin; Oxidative stress; Topical therapy.

1. INTRODUCTION

Atopic dermatitis (AD) is the most widespread chronic inflammatory skin disease., influencing over 200 million people worldwide and constituting approximately 20% of children and 10% of adults. AD associated with skin barrier breakdown, inflammation, and itching (pruritus), pressing complications.^[1] Use of a topical preparation containing Ectoine, a low molecular mass cyclic-amino acid derivative and an extremolyte (one of several osmoprotectants made by extremophiles) has been shown to have favourable effects on skin dryness, pruritus, and dermatitis scores in patients with atopic dermatitis.^[2] Moreover, the pumpkin preparations have also demonstrated outstanding anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and wound healing effects in preclinical studies of dermatitis.^[3]

Pathophysiology of atopic dermatitis

Complex interactions such as skin barrier defect, inflammation and itch are mainly involved in the pathophysiology of AD, The epidermis plays an essential role as a physical and functional barrier, and skin barrier defects are the most significant pathologic findings in AD skin. Filaggrin (FLG) protein plays a crucial role in skin barrier formation and integrity, and its degradation products play a role in water binding capacity and formation of NMF (natural moisturizing factor).^[4]

Fig. (1).^[4]

The cellular and molecular composition of the SC. (A) The outer most layer of the human epidermis, the SC, acts as a key facilitator of bidirectional interactions between the host, its resident microbiome, and the external environment. The plasma membrane of flattened, a nuclear corneocytes is replaced by a lipid-rich cornified envelope, an ordered structural proteins and embedded in an extra cellular lipid bilayer. Adjoining corneocytes are linked by the corneodesmosomes. (B) Structural integrity of the SC is maintained through intracellular aggregation of keratin intermediate filaments, including filaggrin. These are linked to the epidermal proteins scaffold, consisting of proteins encoded for by genes located within the epidermal differentiation complex on chromosome 1q21 and the cornified envelope. Intercellular adhesion is maintained by corneodesmosomes, with corneocytes desquamation being tightly controlled by a balance of intercellular proteases and protease inhibitors. (C) Intracellular filaggrin undergoes degradation into constituent amino acid derivatives as corneocyte differentiation progresses, which, along with their post-translational modified derivatives form major constituents of the epidermal natural moisturizing factor. NMF, natural moisturizing factor; PCA, pyrrolidonecarboxylic acid; SC, stratum corneum; UCA, urocanic acid.

In AD, (FLG) deficiency is a primary factor in impaired skin barrier. Filaggrin loss results in increased trans epidermal water loss (TEWL) and reduced skin hydration, which not only weakens the physical barrier but also increases susceptibility to physical injury (e.g., scratching), External stressors, and microbial proliferation. These changes disrupt the skin barrier and enhance the release of Cytokines from epithelial cells, primarily thymic stromal lymphopoietin (TSLP), IL-25, and IL-33. These cytokines function as stimuli, stimulating immune cells to induce inflammation.^[5] Dendritic cells (DCs) present in the epidermis and dermis react to these epithelial stimuli by enhancing co-stimulatory molecule expression, such as OX-40 ligand (OX40L) and chemokines like CCL17, which drive naïve T cells toward a Th2 immune response. Simultaneously, group 2 innate lymphoid cells (ILC2s) are activated by IL-33, TSLP, and IL-25, releasing IL-13 and IL-5, which further drive the type 2 immune response.^[4,5,6] Th2 cells represent the main immune dysregulation in AD. They release IL-4, IL-13, and IL-24, further impairing the barrier by suppressing filaggrin production.^[5,7] IL-5 initiates the mobilization and activation of eosinophils, leading to tissue inflammation, while IL-31 directly stimulates sensory nerve endings, producing pruritus. IL-4 and IL-13 also enhance B cell class switching to IgE, maintaining allergic sensitization and enhancing mast cell activation.^[8,9] The latter Active immune cells enhance and maintain inflammation: eosinophils secrete cytotoxic granules and cytokines; mast cells, activated by

surface IgE binding, resulting in degranulation and release of histamine and other pro-inflammatory mediators; and sensory nerves mediate chronic itch, leading to a cycle of scratching that worsens barrier impairment. Overall, the filaggrin deficiency pathway leads to increased levels of TSLP, IL-25, IL-33, IgE, and eosinophils, accompanied by chronic epidermal barrier impairment, chronic type 2 inflammation, and intense pruritus— Key characteristics of the pathophysiology of atopic dermatitis.^[7]

Fig. (2).^[7]

A simplistic overview of AD pathogenesis. Non-lesional skin has an epidermal barrier deficiency with a reduced diversity of the microbiome. In acute AD lesion, Langerhans cells, IEDC bearing specific IgE bound to the high affinity receptor for IgE, and dermal dendritic cells bind allergens and antigens. Keratinocyte-derived (IL-18, IL-1 β , IL-33, TSLP and IL-25) and Th2-cell-derived cytokines IL-4, IL-13, and IL-31 directly activate sensory nerves, which promotes pruritus.

During transition to chronicity, itch is amplified by various pruritogens (e.g., antigens and molecular mediators such as histamine and other substances). Scratching exacerbates dermatitis, which may further enhance pruritus and result in an itch/scratch vicious cycle. Chronic AD lesional skin is characterized by the intensification of Th2, Th1, and Th17 responses. DC = dendritic cell, MC = mast cell, IEDC = inflammatory dendritic epidermal cell, ILC = innate lymphoid cell. LC = lymphoid cell, B = B cell, Eo = eosinophile, Ba = basophile, IFN = interferon, IL = interleukin, Th = T-helper cell, Th0 = naive T cell, TNF = tumor necrosis factor, TSLP = thymic stromal lymphopoeitin.

3. Ectoine in topical preparations

Using ectoine in topical preparations can improve atopic dermatitis. According to studies, ectoine has been shown to enhance the skin barrier, reduce transepidermal water loss (TEWL), improve overall skin hydration, and alleviate inflammatory skin conditions. Ectoine mainly exerts its activity via a physical mechanism known as preferential exclusion.^[8,9,10] Its primary function is the complex formation of Ectoine, which involves binding water molecules and creating hydro complexes (Figure 3). These complexes build up a stabilizing hydration shell surrounding biomolecule, such as cells, proteins, and enzymes, thereby providing Ectoine protective and biomolecule-stabilizing effects.

Fig. (3).^[8]

Molecular dynamic simulation of different models containing (A) water, (B) water and ectoine, and (C) water and glycerol. The pictures are taken at the beginning of the simulation ($t = 0$, A1, B1, C1) and after 200 ps (A2), 1000 ps (B2), and 500 ps (C2) at a constant temperature of 370 K. Water clusters around ectoine molecules remain stable for a long period of time, whereas the cluster of water and glycerol breaks down and water molecules diffuse out of the spheres. The pictures represent the number of water molecules counted during the dynamic simulation 1. The solutes are green.

Fig.(4).^[2]

Schematic image of the exclusion model for compatible solutes at membrane surfaces leading to an expansion and thus fluidization of the lipids. Organized water clusters at the membrane surface are formed around the solutes thus increasing the water activity at the membrane surface.

It is also crucial for the efficient closure of wounds.^[10,11,12] Ectoine not only acts at the cellular level (protecting membranes) but also shows measurable *in vivo* barrier-improvement (reduced TEWL) when applied topically. Figure 5 shows that skin pretreated with 2-5% ectoine-containing cream becomes less susceptible to damage by the surfactant SDS. It was shown to a reduction of TEWL to 40% compared to placebo.^[8]

Fig. (5).^[8]

In vivo determination of TEWL after damage of the skin barrier by SDS. The forearm skin of the volunteers ($n = 5$) is treated twice daily for 1 week with an oil in water emulsion (2 mg/cm²) containing 0% (placebo), 2%, and 5% ectoine. To achieve a synthetic increase in TEWL by damaging the skin barrier, the skin is subsequently treated with 2% SDS in water for 24 hours and the TEWL is determined. The diagram shows the TEWL before and after treatment with emulsion containing ectoine and after damage of the skin barrier with SDS.^[17] Also After CO₂ laser treatment on skin, 0-5% cream containing ectoine was applied twice daily and a reduction in TEWL from 6.2 to 5.3 g/(m²·h) was obtained for the preparation containing 5% ectoine. The occurrence of redness after CO₂ laser treatment for reported to be decreased as well.

2.1 Enhancement in skin hydration

Studies have proven that Ectoine can increase skin moisturization by up to 39%. Findings Ectoine maintains skin moisture level significantly higher than non- or placebo-treated areas for more than 24h. In addition, Ectoine helps to prevent a rapid drying of delicate skin after the spreading of hygroscopic silica gel. Long-term skin hydration can be maintained after topical application of Ectoine.^[8] In further experiments, the long-term moisturizing properties of Ectoine were determined. The forearms of the volunteers were treated twice daily with 0.5% and 1% Ectoine for a period up to 12 days. The skin hydration was recorded from day 8 to day 12. Hydration status was again assessed on day 19 after discontinuation of application. Interestingly, by day 12 hydration had risen to >200 vs the placebo-treated group and was sustained for the duration of the study. Nevertheless, after day 12 (with the cessation of topically treatment), over the next following 7 days skin hydration could be kept on this level demonstrating a typical long-term moisturising property of Ectoine.

Fig. (6).^[8]

Long-term moisturizing effect with ectoine. The skin of the volar forearm of five volunteers is treated twice daily for 12 days with a cosmetic formulation (2 mg/cm²) containing 0% (control), 0.5%, and 1% ectoine. The skin hydration is determined by corneometry starting at day 8 until day 12 (A). On this day the application is stopped for 7 days, finalizing this experiment on day 19 with a last measurement of hydration (B).

2.2 Protective Effect of Ectoine Against UVA-Induced Cellular Stress

One of the earliest studies demonstrating cytoprotective effect of Ectoine was conducted by (Buenger, 2004) using human dermal fibroblasts. The researchers observed that the addition of 1 mM Ectoine to the culture medium significantly protected cells from UVA-induced damage. The underlying mechanism was attributed to a reduction in ceramide formation following Ectoine treatment. This finding is noteworthy because ceramides can act as mediators of cellular stress, often compromising mitochondrial integrity and triggering apoptotic cell death or inflammation.^[13]

Although ceramides are widely recognized in cosmetics for their beneficial role in strengthening the skin barrier, it is important to distinguish between their structural and signaling functions. In the stratum corneum, ceramides serve as essential lipids that maintain skin hydration and barrier integrity.^[25] However, in living cells under stress, elevated levels of ceramides act as bioactive molecules that initiate cell death pathways. Therefore, the reduction of stress-induced ceramide formation by Ectoine reflects a cell-protective mechanism, distinct from the barrier-replenishing role of ceramides in topical skincare applications.^[14]

3. Pumpkin seed oil/Extract effect on skin

Pumpkin Seed oil / Extract is a rich source of bioactive that exhibit anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and immunomodulatory effects. It promotes wound healing, reduced cytokine-mediated inflammation, protects against oxidative stress, and improves skin barrier function all of which can contribute to manage atopic dermatitis. Pumpkin plant (*Cucurbita*) is in the family Cucurbitaceae.^[3] The three most common ones we know globally are: the *Curcubita pepo*, *Curcubita Maxima* and the *curcubita Moschata*. Pumpkin seed oils have been praised for their nutritional properties because of their richness in unsaturated fatty acids.^[15] The predominant fatty acids in the pumpkin seed oils were linoleic (C18:2) and oleic (C18:1), followed by stearic (C18:0), palmitic acid (C16:0). The high content of linoleic (C18:2) and oleic acid (C18:1) in pumpkin seed oil may contribute to skin barrier repair and anti-

inflammatory effects.^[16] Moreover, they also comprise several bioactive compounds like β - β -carotene, tocopherols, and phenolics which ultimately lead to antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties. Moreover, they also comprise several bioactive compounds like β - β -carotene, tocopherols, which ultimately lead to antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties.^[15,16]

3.1. Pumpkin seed oil extract on wound healing and immunomodulator effect

Hamdan and Mehdy (2025) explored the therapeutic potential of pumpkin seed oil extract (PSOE) in promoting the healing of trichloroacetic acid (TCA) induced skin wounds. To assess the remedial effects of PSOE, different concentrations (25%, 50%, and 100%) were applied topically and compared against both a commercial wound-healing reference (Mebo®) and an untreated control group. The study revealed that PSOE promoted faster wound closure, improved epithelial regeneration, and reduced inflammatory cell infiltration. The 100% concentration produced the most pronounced benefits, showing nearly complete wound healing. Additionally, biochemical assays demonstrated significant downregulation of pro-inflammatory cytokines such as TNF- α and IL-13, alongside.^[17]

Fig. (7).^[18]

Pumpkin Extract on contact dermatitis and downregulation of cytokines. Ayuob et al. reported in rat model of contact dermatitis paired with chronic stress, topical extract from pumpkin (*Cucurbita pepo* L.) could alleviate skin inflammation. Depression in rats was induced with the help of chronic unpredictable mild stress (CUMS) for four weeks, then 1-fluoro-2,4-dinitrofluorobenzene (DNFB) was applied for two weeks to provoke contact

dermatitis. Studies revealed that the pumpkin-extract-treated skin showed marked improvement compared to untreated dermatitis skin. Specifically, the extract significantly reduced levels of pro-inflammatory cytokines (such as TNF- α and IL-6), down-regulated the expression of COX-2 and inducible nitric oxide synthase (iNOS), and improved antioxidant enzyme levels (SOD, GPX, CAT) while lowering markers of oxidative stress.

3.2. Effect of pumpkin in topical preparation

The study revealed that significant results in Patients for Dermatology life quality index (DLQI) scores in both pumpkin ointment and betamethasone treated group with improved patient overall quality of life with pumpkin ointment. Also, Betamethasone and pumpkin ointment showed significant improvement compared with almond and Eucerin with reduced The Hand Eczema Severity Index (HECSI) scores respectively.^[19]

Also study showed that Combining topical and oral Pumpkin Extract on contact dermatitis and downregulation of cytokines. Previous study states the combined oral and topical application of pumpkin extract in alleviating contact dermatitis associated with depression in rats. The combined oral and topical application of PE significantly reduced the levels of pro-inflammatory cytokines such as TNF- α and IL-6 in both serum and skin tissues compared to the untreated and betamethasone-treated group. Also, Pumpkin Extract treatment enhanced antioxidant enzyme activities, including superoxide dismutase (SOD), catalase (CAT) and glutathione peroxidase (Gpx) while decreasing malondialdehyde (MDA) levels indicating reduction in oxidative stress.^[20]

A study stated that the essential fatty acids in pumpkin seeds help to support skin barrier function and reduce inflammation, which further supports its potential use in managing symptoms.

4. CONCLUSION

Complex interactions such as skin barrier defect, inflammation, and itch are mainly involved in the pathophysiology of AD. In atopic dermatitis (AD), filaggrin (FLG) deficiency is a primary factor in impaired skin barrier. the filaggrin deficiency pathway leads to increased levels of TSLP, IL-25, IL-33, IgE, and eosinophils, Accompanied by chronic epidermal barrier impairment, chronic type 2 inflammation, and intense pruritus. Key characteristics of the pathophysiology of atopic dermatitis using topical ectoine help to relieve inflammatory disease associated with impaired skin barrier, reduce TEWL and improve overall skin

condition using pumpkin extract helps to downregulate cytokines, improving inflammation and itching, help to repair skin barrier so combining ectoine and pumpkin together in one formulation may have good impact in improving atopic dermatitis

5. Abbreviations

6. REFERENCE

1. 4. Sroka-Tomaszewska, J., & Trzeciak, M. (2021). Molecular mechanisms of atopic dermatitis pathogenesis. *International journal of molecular sciences*, 22(8): 4130.
2. Harishchandra, R. K., Wulff, S., Lentzen, G., Neuhaus, T., & Galla, H. J. (2010). The effect of compatible solute ectoines on the structural organization of lipid monolayer and bilayer membranes. *Biophysical chemistry*, 150(1-3): 37-46.
3. de Oliveira, M. L. M., Nunes-Pinheiro, D. C. S., Bezerra, B. M. O., Leite, L. O., Tomé, A. R., & Girão, V. C. C. (2013). Topical anti-inflammatory potential of pumpkin (*Cucurbita pepo* L.) seed oil on acute and chronic skin inflammation in mice. *Acta Scientiae Veterinariae*, 41(1): 1-9.
4. Stefanovic, N., & Irvine, A. D. (2024). Filaggrin and beyond: new insights into the skin barrier in atopic dermatitis and allergic diseases, from genetics to therapeutic perspectives. *Annals of Allergy, Asthma & Immunology*, 132(2): 187-195.
5. Kim, J., Kim, B. E., & Leung, D. Y. (2019, March). Pathophysiology of atopic dermatitis: Clinical implications. In *Allergy and asthma proceedings*, (Vol. 40, No. 2: 84).
6. Schuler IV, C. F., Billi, A. C., Maverakis, E., Tsoi, L. C., & Gudjonsson, J. E. (2023). Novel insights into atopic dermatitis. *Journal of Allergy and Clinical Immunology*, 151(5): 1145-1154.
7. Fania, L., Moretta, G., Antonelli, F., Scala, E., Abeni, D., Albanesi, C., & Madonna, S. (2022). Multiple roles for cytokines in atopic dermatitis: from pathogenic mediators to endotype-specific biomarkers to therapeutic targets. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 23(5): 2684.
8. Graf, R., Anzali, S., Buenger, J., Pfluecker, F., & Driller, H. (2008). The multifunctional role of ectoine as a natural cell protectant. *Clinics in dermatology*, 26(4): 326-333.
9. Załęska, I., Goik, U., Goik, T., & Wilkus, K. (2025). The Influence of Ectoine on the Skin Parameters Damaged by a CO2 Laser. *Molecules*, 30(11): 2470.

10. Kauth, M., & Trusova, O. V. (2022). Topical ectoine application in children and adults to treat inflammatory diseases associated with an impaired skin barrier: a systematic review. *Dermatology and therapy*, 12(2): 295-313.
11. Kolp, S., Pietsch, M., Galinski, E. A., & Gütschow, M. (2006). Compatible solutes as protectants for zymogens against proteolysis. *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta (BBA)-Proteins and Proteomics*, 1764(7): 1234-1242.
12. Kahraman, E., Kaykın, M., Şahin Bektay, H., & Güngör, S. Recent Advances on Topical Application of Ceramides to Restore Barrier Function of Skin. *Cosmetics*, 2019; 6: 52.
13. Buenger, J., & Driller, H. (2004). Ectoin: an effective natural substance to prevent UVA-induced premature photoaging. *Skin pharmacology and physiology*, 17(5): 232-237.
14. Hannun, Y. A., & Obeid, L. M. (2002). The ceramide-centric universe of lipid-mediated cell regulation: stress encounters of the lipid kind. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*, 277(29): 25847-25850.
15. Singh, A., & Kumar, V. (2023). Phyto-chemical and bioactive compounds of pumpkin seed oil as affected by different extraction methods. *Food Chemistry Advances*, 2: 100211.
16. Amin, M. Z., Islam, T., Uddin, M. R., Uddin, M. J., Rahman, M. M., & Satter, M. A. (2019). Comparative study on nutrient contents in the different parts of indigenous and hybrid varieties of pumpkin (*Cucurbita maxima* Linn.). *Heliyon*, 5(9).
17. Hamdan, S. A., & Mehdy, S. S. (2025). The Effects of Pumpkin Seed Oil Extract on Trichloroacetic Acid-Induced Skin Wounds and Associated Immune Markers were Evaluated Using ELISA. *Asian Journal of Advances in Research*, 8(1): 417-429.
18. Al-Turky, H. M., Abo Chameh, G., & Ibrahim, B. (2022). Effect of defatting and extracting solvent on the antioxidant activities in seed extracts of two species of Syrian pumpkin. *Journal of Food Measurement and Characterization*, 16(6): 4813-4821.
19. Amin, M. Z., Islam, T., Uddin, M. R., Uddin, M. J., Rahman, M. M., & Satter, M. A. (2019). Comparative study on nutrient contents in the different parts of indigenous and hybrid varieties of pumpkin (*Cucurbita maxima* Linn.). *Heliyon*, 5(9).
20. Ayuob, N., Hawuit, E., Mohammedsaleh, Z. M., Shaalan, D., Hawasah, M. M. H., Basheikh, K. A. A., & Shaker, S. A. (2022). L. *Cucurbita pepo* modulates contact dermatitis in depressed rats through downregulation of proinflammatory cytokines and upregulation of antioxidant status. *Advances in Dermatology and Allergology/Postępy Dermatologii i Alergologii*, 39(2): 286-297.

21. Khademi, A., Mansuri, P., Pahlevan, D., Bozorgi, M., Nasiri, M., Hejazi, S., ... & Shirbeigi, L. (2020). Efficacy of pumpkin ointment in treatment of chronic hand eczema: A randomized, active-controlled, double blind clinical trial. *Iranian Journal of Public Health*, 49(7): 1339.
22. Balgoon, M. J., Al-Zahrani, M. H., Jaouni, S. A., & Ayuob, N. (2021). Combined oral and topical application of pumpkin (*Cucurbita pepo* L.) Alleviates contact dermatitis associated with depression through downregulation pro-inflammatory cytokines. *Frontiers in Pharmacology*, 12: 663417.
23. Zawawi, N. A., Ahmad, H., Madatheri, R., Fadilah, N. I. M., Maarof, M., & Fauzi, M. B. (2025). Flavonoids as Natural Anti-Inflammatory Agents in the Atopic Dermatitis Treatment. *Pharmaceutics*, 17(2): 261.